

Supporting Information

Non Heteroepitaxial CsPbBr₃/Cs₄PbBr₆ Interfaces Will Result in Non Passivated Bright Bromide Vacancies

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Calculation of Urbach energy:

Calculating Urbach energy (Urbach tail) was followed according to procedure set by ref [1]:

Absorption coefficient is defined as:

$$(1) \alpha = \ln(10) * \frac{A_s}{t}$$

where A_s is the measured absorbance and t the material's thickness.

$$(2) \alpha = \alpha_0 \exp\left(\frac{\hbar\nu}{E_U}\right)$$

Where α_0 is a pre-exponential constant, $\hbar\nu$ is the photon energy and E_U is the Urbach energy which can be found from the slope of the α Vs. $\hbar\nu$ plot.

Fitting of the TRCL spectra

Fitting of the TRCL spectra:

$$(3) f = \text{erfc}\left(-\frac{t}{p}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^{n_{Exp}} A_i e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}$$

Where the erfc function defines the rise time, while p is the pulse's width. A_i and τ_i are the fitted amplitudes and time constants of the decay.

Figure S1 - Schematic illustration of the synthesis process where the DMSO based 0.065M precursor solution is introduced to a container containing a substrate submerged in acetone solution. Afterwards, the MC's settle on the substrate. Given enough time (>10min), Cs-rich fins start to form.

EDS measurements

EDS measurements were taken at 10KeV with a working distance of 10mm and a spot size of 4.5nm using a FEI Quanta200 microscope.

CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals:

Figure S2 – SEM micrograph depicting the different EDS points of acquisition for several CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals. All measurements are very close to the theoretical value for atomic ratios in CsPbBr₃ as depicted in table S1.

Table S1 – CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals EDS measurements results summary:

Spectrum#	Br [%at]	Cs [%at]	Pb [%at]
1	60.7	20.4	18.9
2	59.1	20.9	20.1
3	59	22	19
4	60.4	20.7	18.9
5	61.3	19.1	19.6
6	61.5	19.9	20.4
7	60.4	20.3	19.4
Mean	60.3	20.5	19.5
Std. deviation	0.98	0.90	0.60
Max.	61.5	22	20.4
Min.	59	19.1	18.9
IDEAL CsPbBr3	60	20	20

Cs₄PbBr₆ 'fins':

Figures S3 - (a, b) SEM micrograph depicting the different EDS points of acquisition for several Cs₄PbBr₆ 'fins'. Most measurements are very close to the theoretical value for atomic ratios in CsPbBr₃ as depicted in table S2. We ascribe the larger deviations to the fins' low thickness that might add errors due to a shared interaction volume with the perovskite underneath.

Table S2 – Cs₄PbBr₆ 'fins' EDS measurements results summary

Spectrum#	Br [%at]	Cs [%at]	Pb [%at]
a - 1	49.6	40	10.4
a - 2	56	33.6	10.4
a - 3	52.1	37	10.9
b - 1	54.4	34.2	11.3
b - 2	54.9	35.5	9.7
Mean	53.4	36.1	10.5
Std. deviation	2.6	2.6	0.6
Max.	56	40	11.3
Min.	49.6	33.6	9.7
IDEAL Cs₄PbBr₆	54.5	36.4	9.1

CsPb₂Br₅ films:

Figures S4 – (a, b) SEM micrograph depicting the different EDS points of acquisition for several CsPb₂Br₅ sheets. The measurements are very close to the theoretical value for atomic ratios in CsPbBr₃ as depicted in table S3.

Table S3 – CsPb₂Br₅ films EDS measurements results summary

Spectrum	Br [%at]	Cs [%at]	Pb [%at]
1	64.7	12	23.3
2	63	13.1	24
3	64.3	11.6	24.1
4	64.3	11.1	24.6
5	62.9	11.9	25.1
Mean	63.8	11.9	24.2
Std. deviation	0.8	0.7	0.7
Max.	64.7	13.1	25.1
Min.	62.9	11.1	23.3
IDEAL CsPb₂Br₅	62.5	12.5	25

Figure S5 – SEM micrograph of a Cs_4PbBr_6 fin. Beside the rough surface which all fins exhibit, this fin also houses triangular shaped inclusion that we hypothesis to be CsPbBr_3 .

Figure S6 – XRD patterns with identification markers of deposited LHP particles on a glass substrate where substrate was removed immediately after precursor solution was injected (i.e, short reaction time). CsPbBr_3 (ICDD 04-014-9676). Cs_4PbBr_6 (ICDD 04-015-9683). CsPb_2Br_5 (ICDD 00-054-0753).

Figure S7 – Confocal PL measurement taken from an isolated CsPbBr_3 micro-crystal. Measurement show identical PL spectra compared to the measurements taken from the entire sample using a spectrometer. This helps in validating that the other phases in the sample have no effect on the measured PL.

Figure S8 – TEM diffractions taken from CsPbBr₃ micro-crystal lamella fabricated using FIB. (a) Low magnification TEM image of the lamella. Areas marked as (1), (2) were used to take diffraction patterns (c), (d). (b) SEM micrograph of the fabricated lamella. Diffractions (c) and (e) corresponds to zone axes [001] and [110] respectively. Marked by green circles are forbidden reflections caused by double diffraction due to thicker samples artefacts.

Table S4 –interface EDS results summary

Area	Br [%at]	Pb [%at]	Cs [%at]
1	59.7 ± 7.0	21.4 ± 2.5	18.9 ± 2.5
2	55.7 ± 6.6	10.6 ± 1.4	33.6 ± 4.6

Figure S9 – EDS map of the CsPbBr₃/Cs₄PbBr₆ interface, where acquisition area#1 was taken from the CsPbBr₃ region, and acquisition area#2 was taken from the Cs₄PbBr₆ region. Areas where averaged EDS spectra were taken are marked. Values calculated using Bote-Salvat ionization cross-section model using the Thermo Fisher’s Velox® software

Figure S10 – TEM diffraction of the CsPbBr_3 and Cs_4PbBr_6 sides of the interface (see following figure). (a) Diffraction of CsPbBr_3 with zone axis of $[\bar{1}00]$. (b) Diffraction of Cs_4PbBr_6 with zone axis of $[\bar{2}10]$. Marked by green circles are forbidden reflections caused by double diffraction.

Figure S11 – (a, b) HRTEM micrographs of the $CsPbBr_3/Cs_4PbBr_6$ interface area. In (a) marked by green is the Cs_4PbBr_6 phase and in blue the $CsPbBr_3$ phase. Evident by the micrographs is the different phase contrast between the two regions.

Figure S13 – (a/b) Temperature/excitation dependent PL spectra of CsPbBr₃ micro crystals. Dotted markers are the experimental values, and the lines are the Gaussian fitting functions. (a inset) Peak position in wavelength vs. temperature. (b inset) Integrated intensities of each peak (BE, FX, BX) vs. excitation power density fitted with a power law. The arrow in (b) marks the limits of the excitation power density where, the lowest PL curve was excited with 8.3 W/cm² and the highest PL curve was excited with 663.0 W/cm²

Figure S14- Colorized CL micrograph of a CsPbBr₃ micro-crystal cluster. (b, c) micrographs of the intensity integrated over (b) band 1 (~535nm), (c) band 2 (~540nm). (c) SEM micrographs acquired simultaneously.

Figure S15 – (a) Locations of collected point spectra in the low temperature CL measurements. (b) Colorized band micrograph depicting the filtered intensity from the measure cluster at 560 (nm). (c) Spectrum of the collected points.

Supplementary reference

- (1) Natsume, Y.; Sakata, H.; Hirayama, T. Low-Temperature Electrical Conductivity and Optical Absorption Edge of ZnO Films Prepared by Chemical Vapour Deposition. *Phys. Status Solidi* **1995**, *148* (2), 485–495. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2211480217>.